

SOCIAL PROBLEMS FACED BY HIV-POSITIVE INMATES IN DISTRICT PRISONS & CORRECTIONAL FACILITY MALIR KARACHI

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to explore the Social Problems Faced by HIV-positive Inmates in District Prisons & Correctional Facility Malir Karachi. A quantitative cum/qualitative study was conducted using an indigenously developed tool for interview to collect primary data from a sample of 64 inmates, however the total population of the facility was 110 HIV-positive prisoners as provided by the prison management. The study results showed that most of the adult inmates 45.31% were aged between 26-33 years, followed by 23.44% aged between 34-41 years with a mean age of 32.70 years and a standard deviation of 7.57 years mainly married 51.67%, and live in various locations within Karachi such as, 21.875% each from Korangi and Landhi, 9.375% in Bhens Colony, while 6.25% of respondents each were from Baldia, Kemari, and Orangi. Ethnic diversity was notable, with 31.25% identifying as "Other" including Barmi, Bengali, Hazara, Saraiki, 25% as Pashtun, 23.437% Baloch, Punjabi 9.375%, Sindhi 7.813%, and 6.25% were Urdu Speaking. Educational attainment was noticeably low, 57.812% had no formal education, and just 34.375% completed secondary education. Of the inmates, most respondents 43.75% engaged in labor before imprisonment,

Family structure showed that 71.875% lived in joint family structures. Given the economic state, 70.312% owned their homes, while 37.5% reported earnings above 60,000 PKR. Notably, all respondents shared single barrack in prison having a capacity of around 60 inmates, and 50% felt that overcrowding somehow affect their health. Drug use was prevalent, with 93.75% using substances before incarceration, predominantly methamphetamine 68.75%, where almost 63% used injection before imprisonment. Awareness of HIV status was high, with 56.25% knowing their status prior to imprisonment, and 98.437% receiving treatment while incarcerated.

INTRODUCTION

A prisoner is a person who commits a crime and is sentenced to prison by the state's justice system for the offense (Harigovind, 2012). Offenders are lawfully

detained in prison as a kind of punishment for their crimes. It is also known as a correctional facility, where criminals are detained until they are found

guilty or until their cases are tried. In order to keep inmates from escaping, it is typically surrounded by walls, fencing, and a variety of other physical features or barriers, such as motion sensors, dogs, roving patrols, armed guard towers, concertina wires, electrified fencing, security cameras, and security lighting (Hanser, 2012; McShane & Williams, 2004). The incarceration of convicted individuals is a global occurrence, present in nearly every society worldwide (Walmsley, 2013; McLeod et al., 2020). According to the Global Prison Trends Report, as of early 2020, approximately 11 million people were incarcerated, with the majority being under trial (Global Prison Trends 2020 - Penal Reform International, 2022).

In 2009, during the 8th commission on crime prevention and criminal justice, it was mentioned that overcrowding in prisons has very serious effects on the health and conduct of the inmates living there and produces other security difficulties as well. "Prisoners shall provide all the accommodation facilities like sleeping place, medical attention, the environment condition, requisite floor space, ventilation, heating, and lighting," according to Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners (SMR) Rule 10. There are not many studies in Pakistan that concentrate on disease detection, treatment, community links, health, education, and prevention for prisoners. In Pakistan, a serious issue is the spread of HIV/AIDS, also known as acquired immunodeficiency syndrome, among individuals who engage in high-risk behaviors. According to recent data by UNAIDS, the prevalence of HIV rate among adults aged between 15-49 years is 0.2% (UNAIDS, n.d.-b). Over the years, AIDS was rare and widespread in Pakistan's major populations. However, new data indicates that the disease is now spreading from key populations to multiple sexual partners and their intimate partners (National AIDS Control Program Pakistan: Pakistan AIDS Strategy III (2015-2021), 2017). Pakistan, which has been the hub of multiple HIV outbreaks over the past 20 years, has seen about 210,000 cases of HIV infection. In actuality, the nation has experienced four outbreaks since 2018 (Mir et al., 2019). Data Hub for the Asia Pacific, n.d.). Prisons serve as breeding grounds for infectious diseases. Compared to the general population, there is a higher prevalence and widespread spread of HIV, HBV, HCV, and TB in prisons worldwide. Along with the difficulties

encountered in a correctional facility, there are chances for early identification and treatment of these extremely contagious diseases, which would benefit not only convicts and prison workers, but also family members and the public population due to the rapid turnover of prisoners (Wali et al., 2019). Available data show that 3% of prisoners worldwide are expected to be HIV positive, and 1 in 4 inmates are HCV-positive (People in Prisons and Other Closed Settings, 2022b). In Sindh, recent data from office of the Inspectorate General Prisons & Correction Services showed that the total number of inmates suffering from HIV/AIDS in the province was 228 which almost the 1% of the total population.

In order to prevent HIV/AIDS in the major jails of Sindh Province, such as District Jail Malir, the Sindh AIDS Control Program has created service delivery packages for drug users and prisoners (HIV/AIDS in Pakistan, 2012). However, in light of this, this study, the first of its kind in Sindh, set out to evaluate the social problems that HIV-positive prisoners in the district and correctional facility in Malir Karachi experience.

Literature Review

Pakistan's prison system is among the most overcrowded in the world. Many of the 91 jails and prisons in the country were over capacity as of 2022. Prisoners' pre-existing health issues have been made worse by extreme overcrowding, which leaves prisoners susceptible to infections and unable to get basic medical care. Some of the worst of these abuses, which long predated the pandemic and have continued without correction thereafter, were made public by the Covid-19 epidemic of 2020. In addition to causing additional damage to many facilities, particularly in Sindh province, the mid-2020s floods in Pakistan further isolated and exposed the jail population to water-borne illnesses ("A Nightmare for Everyone," 2023). Poor health care is a major sign of a malfunctioning criminal justice system and is linked to a number of other rights violations against inmates, such as torture and mistreatment. Serious human rights violations in prisons and jails, such as inadequate and substandard food, unsanitary living conditions, and restricted access to medications and treatment, are made worse by corruption among prison officials and guards as well as impunity for

abusive behavior. The health care issue in prisons also reflects broader shortcomings in Pakistan's health care system, which was most recently made worse by an economic crisis that rocked the country's economy in 2022. Pakistan has been allocating a little portion of its GDP—less than 3 percent—to health care for decades, far less than the recommended level set by the World Health Organization (WHO) (“A Nightmare for Everyone,” 2023).

Usually, when the general public thinks about prisons, images of overcrowded facilities with tall walls and barbed wire come to mind. They also usually envision an entirely male prison population, with the majority of inmates having tattoos. According to UNODC estimates, there were over 11.7 million people incarcerated worldwide in 2019. This number is equivalent to the population of whole countries like Bolivia, Burundi, Belgium, or Tunisia. Comparing the current estimate to 2000, when there were about 9.3 million prisoners worldwide, shows a rise of more than 25% (“Data Matters,” 2021). Global jail populations as of 2019 were projected to be 0.8 million women and 10.9 million men. The percentage of men incarcerated climbed by almost 22%, compared to the nearly 60% growth in the number of women and girls, and over 740,000 women and girls are incarcerated worldwide (Fair et al., 2022). With 2,068,800 inmates, the United States leads the world in terms of jail population in 2023. Moreover, China (1,690,000), Brazil (811,707), India (478,600), and Russia (471,490) are the nations with the highest prisoner populations (Incarceration | Judiciaries Worldwide, n.d.). (Elad, 2023).

In Southern Asia, the number of men incarcerated increased from 600,000 in 2000 to 880,000 in 2019. During that time, the rate of increase in the male population exceeded both the global and Asia-Pacific area growth rates, which were 25% and 39%, respectively (Kim et al., 2022). Pakistan's total prison population is 100,366 prisoners, based on primary data collected from 127 jails across all provinces and A&J. Punjab jails house 58,534 inmates as of November 2023, accounting for 58% of Pakistan's total prison population. Punjab's jails are running at 159% of their maximum capacity, with 42,175 people (or 72%) awaiting conviction after being placed on trial (Prison Population of Pakistan, 2023). Sindh houses a prison population of 24,904 distributed

among its 23 operational jails. Of this total, 80% are under-trial prisoners.

HIV/AIDS

HIV is a virus that gradually reduces the function of human immune system cells after infecting them. AIDS is a condition that can happen as a result of an HIV infection when your immune system is severely weakened (Professional, n.d.). HIV infection results in immunological deficiencies that make a person more susceptible to a variety of illnesses. HIV can spread through the exchange of infected blood, injecting drug users, semen, vaginal secretions, or breast milk. Unprotected sexual encounters, sharing needles for tattooing and piercing, injecting drugs, receiving blood transfusions, receiving unsafe medical care (such as using syringes and other medical equipment that hasn't been properly sterilized in a medical setting), and accidentally puncturing with contaminated medical wastes are some of the situations where this happens. Because injecting drug users (IDUs) are disproportionately represented in prisons, the prevalence of HIV and other blood-borne illnesses is typically higher among inmates than in the general population (HIV And Prisoners, n.d.).

The extent of HIV transmission during incarceration remains unknown, some evidence suggests that most transmission in criminal justice populations occurs outside of correctional facilities (Hammett, 2006). Nonetheless, it is known that condomless intercourse, risky tattooing, and injectable drug use can result in HIV infection in prisoners; among these risk behaviors, injectable drug use and condomless intercourse are the most frequently mentioned (Braithwaite & Arriola, 2003; Underhill, Dumont, & Operario, 2014). In 2010, 91.3% of all HIV-positive prison inmates in U.S were male, and 8.7% were female (Maruschak, 2012). There is also some evidence that HIV transmission among men who have sex with men (MSM) contributes significantly to new infections (Lima et al., 2015). Prisons can become breeding grounds for HIV/AIDS, tuberculosis (TB), and other infectious diseases. For instance, the incidence of TB, which thrives in cramped, overcrowded conditions, can be up to 10 times higher in prisons than in the general population, and prisoners with HIV have an increased likelihood of developing active TB and experiencing life-

threatening outcomes (Mwatenga et al., 2024).

The Province of Sindh is now experiencing an HIV/AIDS epidemic. The government of Sindh has launched an initiative to provide HIV/AIDS prevention services to prisoners. In a study set out to determine the baseline HIV prevalence in prisoners in Sindh, 15000 prisoners in nine jails spread across six cities in Sindh were offered anonymous unlinked volunteer testing; 4987 (33%) of them accepted to get tested for HIV using the Abbot Determine quick testing kit. The jails in Karachi (0.7%), Sukkur (0.14%, n = 7), Larkana (0.08%, n = 4), Hyderabad (0.06%, n = 3), Shikarpur (0.04%, n = 2), and Khairpur (0.02%, n = 1) accounted for the majority of HIV +positive patients (n = 32). Only three foreigners were identified as HIV+ among the female inmates. In the study sample, the total HIV prevalence was 1% (n = 49) (Prevalence of HIV/AIDS Among Jail Inmates in Sindh, 2009). This study confirms the existence of HIV among Sindh jail inmates and highlights the need for a thorough behavioral analysis to evaluate risk in this community. However, according to recent data in July 2024, from office of Inspector General Prisons and Correctional Services Sindh, there are around 228 inmates with HIV/AIDS +positive incarcerated within the prisons of Sindh.

Drug Abuse

Substance abuse and cigarette smoking are now recognized as significant public health issues. According to a 2017 status report, the estimated global prevalence of episodic alcohol use and daily tobacco smoking among adults was 18.4% and 15.2%, respectively. Additionally, communicable diseases like hepatitis B, hepatitis C, and HIV continue to contribute to the global disease burden, largely due to the intravenous abuse of illicit drugs (Peacock et al., 2018). In a study conducted in Karachi jails to assess the prevalence and risk levels of substance abuse among prisoners it was revealed that a significant majority of prisoners (91.7%) reported having used at least one type of drug in their lifetime. Among the substances currently abused by inmates, tobacco emerged as the most frequently abused, with the highest risk score (15.99 ± 8.14). This was followed by cannabis (8.1 ± 11.46) and opioids (5.67

± 12.19). When categorizing the level of risk, opioid abuse was identified as the most prevalent in the high-risk category, affecting 13% of the prisoners. Cannabis and tobacco followed closely, with 12.7% and 9.5% of inmates, respectively, falling into the high-risk group. However, within the medium-risk category, tobacco use was the most common, with 80.5% of prisoners at risk, followed by cannabis at 35.2% (Jamal et al., 2022).

A person with HIV may experience negative health effects from substance use in a number of ways, such as reduced liver or immunological function or negative reactions to HIV medications (HIV And Substance Use | NIH, n.d.-c). HIV weakens immunity, which makes it more difficult for the body to fight against infections and several types of cancer. Drugs and alcohol can reverse the effects of HIV medications, which can successfully boost immune function (HIV And Substance Use | NIH, n.d.-c). It is estimated that around 20% of new HIV infections are linked to intravenous drug use, a common method of substance abuse. In the United States, more than 1.5 million people abuse stimulants like methamphetamine (meth) and cocaine (NSDUH Annual National Report, 2018).

Hygiene

Personal hygiene can be defined as the practice of keeping one's own body clean. Personal hygiene risks are directly linked to some significant daily activities that are involved in worthy operational actions and mandatory responsibilities. These include brushing teeth at least twice a day, particularly after breakfast and after meals, taking a regular bath with soap, keeping nails short, exercising frequently, and washing hands with soap before meals and after defecation (Perera et al., 2013). Poor hygiene habits and inadequate sanitary conditions are major contributors to the rising incidence of infectious diseases in jail. The health of inmates is negatively impacted by the often-inadequate hygiene conditions in jails. Prisons are not conducive to well-being, with overcrowding and poor sanitation being widespread issues. As a result, communicable diseases frequently spread among prisoners (Behnke et al., 2018).

Theoretical Framework

THEORY	VARIABLE	RESEARCHES
1. Strain Theory (Robert. K Merton 1938)	Overcrowding	1. McGrath, S. A., Marcum, C. D., & Copes, H. (2011). 2. Geegbe et al. (2022b)
1. Anomie Theory	Substance Abuse	1. Hussain et al. (2023c)
2. Theory of Planned Behavior	Hygiene	1. Aluko et al. (2018)

The Theoretical Framework of this study based on these 6 variables which are further explained below: Prison overcrowding increases a number of health concerns and creates an atmosphere where ailments, especially HIV, can spread quickly among prisoners. Drug use and needle sharing, tattooing using unsterile equipment, high-risk sex, and rape make prisons a high-risk setting for HIV transmission. The immune system is weakened by violence, drug abuse, stress, starvation, and overcrowding, which increases the risk of illness for those living with HIV (People in Jails and Prisons – International Association of Providers of AIDS Care, n.d.). Additionally, it makes prisoners' psychological stress worse. Stress, anxiety, and tension are increased because of the small space, lack of privacy, and continual exposure to noise and conflict. Long-term stress may deteriorate mental health, make people more aggressive, and increase the number of violent incidents that occur in prison. The limited resources and services that are available are further strained by overcrowding, which has detrimental effects on inmate well-being including inadequate access to rehabilitation programs, poor nourishment, and inadequate healthcare (Pekala-Wojciechowska et al., 2021). Different theories provide different explanations of overcrowding that may cause problems for inmates in various contexts. For example, according to Merton's Strain Theory, people develop strain when they are not able to achieve culturally acceptable goals through the socially approved means and as a result, they find an alternative way that are not socially acceptable to achieve those goals. (Nickerson, 2023).

In the context of HIV-positive inmates, overcrowding in prisons creates different barriers that may lead to increase in stress and make the prisoner's social problems worse. According to the theory, people who are under stress could turn to abnormal behavior—like drug use—as a coping method. According to a study involving 208 adult parolees, there is a higher chance

of violence and drug/alcohol usage among those who have experienced or witnessed violence in jail. Furthermore, the stress brought on by confined spaces and insufficient resources worsens the negative impacts of overcrowding by encouraging negative feelings and maladaptive behaviors like substance misuse. This supports the claim made by GST that stressors like overcrowding push prisoners to use unhealthy coping mechanisms (McGrath et al., 2011). Another study conducted at Monrovia Central Prison revealed that the main cause of poor jail conditions is overpopulation. In addition to causing or exacerbating mental health issues, overcrowding and associated issues like privacy invasion can also raise the prevalence of violence, self-harm, and suicide. Furthermore, HIV, malaria, and infectious diseases like tuberculosis are among the leading causes of death in prison (Geegbe et al., 2022).

Substance abuse can lead to criminality through various interconnected mechanisms. Using drugs or alcohol can make people do things they wouldn't normally do, like stealing or causing trouble. There is a strong connection between drug abuse and crime. Individuals who abuse drugs often commit crimes to pay for their addiction, which harms society. Additionally, many offenders are under the influence of drugs when they commit crimes (World Drug Report 2012, n.d.). HIV causes a significant percentage of infectious diseases worldwide. Inmates who inject illicit drugs have a significant risk of becoming infected with HIV. With over 10.2 million inmates worldwide, prisons are a high-risk environment for HIV transmission (Hussain et al., 2023b).

Hygiene has a variety of benefits, such as promoting physical health by preventing infections and diseases that can result from poor hygiene. Moreover, it also contributes to mental well-being, as feeling clean and well-groomed can boost confidence and comfort (Silaban et al., 2020). The Theory of Planned

Behavior (TPB) provide the explanations of hygiene that may cause problems for inmates in various contexts. According to the theory a person's actions are determined by their intention, which is shaped by

their attitude toward the behavior, social pressure (subjective norms), and their perceived control over the behavior.

Data Analysis
Contingency Table 1

DRUG	Type of Crime		
	Most severe	Severe	Total
Heroin	3	3	6
Cannabis (charas/bhang)	10	4	14
Cocaine	0	1	1
Methamphetamine (ice/crystal)	14	25	39
Prescription drugs	0	0	0
Others (please specify)	0	0	0
Not Applicable	1	3	4
Total	28	36	64
Mean	4	5.142857143	4.571428571

df1 = k - 1 = 2 - 1 = 1
df2 = N - k = 14 - 2 = 12

Most Severe	(X - 4)	(X - 4) ²
3	-1	1
10	6	36
0	-4	16
14	10	100
0	-4	16
0	-4	16
1	-3	9
Total	0	194

Thus, $\sum(x - X_1)^2 = 194$

Severe	(X - 5.142857143)	(X - 5.142857143) ²
3	-2.14286	4.591837
4	-1.14286	1.306122
1	-4.14286	17.16327
25	19.85714	394.3061
0	-5.14286	26.44898
0	-5.14286	26.44898
3	-2.14286	4.591837
Total	0	474.8571

Thus, $\sum(x - X_2)^2 = 474.8571$
 $SSB = \sum n (X_j - X)^2 = SSB = 7 (4 - 4.571)^2 + 7 (5.1428 - 4.571)^2$
 $SSB = 4.571428571$

$SSE = \sum(X - X_j)^2 = SSE = 194 + 474.857$

$SSE = 668.8571429$

Source	SS	df	MS	F
MS Between Treatment	4.5714	1	4.5714	
Error (Residual)	668.8571	12	55.73809167	4.5714/55.7380
Total	673.4285	13		0.082015725

$F = 0.082015725$

Critical Value = 4.75

The f value is 0.082015725 and the critical-value is 4.75. The result is not significant at $p < .05$, therefore, we will accept the Null Hypothesis.

Contingency Table 2

DRUG	DRUG INJECTING		
	IDU	NON-IDU	Total
Heroin	3	3	6
Cannabis (charas/bhang)	5	9	14
Cocaine	0	1	1
Methamphetamine (ice/crystal)	32	7	39
Prescription drugs	0	0	0
Others (please specify)	0	0	0
Total	40	20	60
Mean	6.666666667	3.333333333	10

$df1 = k - 1 = 2 - 1 = 1$

$df2 = N - k = 12 - 2 = 10$

IDU	$(X - 6.666666667)$	$(X - 6.666666667)^2$
3	-3.666666667	13.44444
5	-1.666666667	2.777778
0	-6.666666667	44.44444
32	25.33333333	641.7778
0	-6.666666667	44.44444
0	-6.666666667	44.44444
Total	0	791.3333

Thus, $\sum(x - X_1)^2 = 791.3333$

Non IDU	$(X - 3.333333333)$	$(X - 3.333333333)^2$
3	-0.33333	0.111111
9	5.666667	32.11111
1	-2.33333	5.444444
7	3.666667	13.44444
0	-3.33333	11.11111
0	-3.33333	11.11111
Total	0	73.33333

Thus, $\sum(x - X_2)^2 = 73.33333$

$SSB = \sum n (X_j - X)^2 = SSB = 6 (6.666666667 - 10)^2 + 6 (3.333333333 - 10)^2$

$SSB = 333.3333$

$SSE = \sum(X - X_i)^2 = SSE = 791.3333 + 73.33333$

$SSE = 864.6666667$

Source	SS	df	MS	F
MS Between Treatment	333.3333	1	333.3333	
Error (Residual)	864.6666667	10	86.46666667	333.3333/86.46666667
Total	1197.999967	11		3.85504973

$F = 3.85504973$

Critical Value = 4.96

The f value is **3.85504973** and the critical-value is 4.96. The result is not significant at $p < .05$, therefore, we will accept the Null Hypothesis.

Contingency table 03

Income	Type of Crime		
	Most Severe	Severe	Total
Below 40,000 PKR	8 (9.187)	13 (11.812)	21
40,001 - 60,000 PKR	10(5.625)	8(6.468)	18
Above 60,000 PKR	10(3.906)	15 (5.859)	25
Total	28	36	64

$$\chi^2 = \frac{(8 - 9.187)^2}{9.187} + \frac{(10 - 5.625)^2}{5.625} + \frac{(10 - 3.906)^2}{3.906} + \frac{(13 - 11.812)^2}{11.812} + \frac{(8 - 6.468)^2}{6.468} + \frac{(15 - 5.859)^2}{5.859}$$

$\chi^2 = 27.80759051$

$df = (C - 1)(R - 1) = (2 - 1)(3 - 1) = 1 \times 2 = 2$

$\chi^2 \alpha = 0.05 = 5.99$

Since, the calculated value of chi-square 27.80759051 is greater than table value 5.99 at 2 degree of freedom and $\alpha = 0.05$, therefore, it is concluded that the Income of accused HIV inmates is related with type of crime committed by them.

The study results showed that most of the inmates 45.31% were aged 26-33, mainly married 51.67%, while 46.9% identified as single, and live in various locations within Karachi. Ethnic diversity was notable, with 31.25% identifying as "Other" including Barmi, Bengali, Hazara, Saraiki and 25% as Pashtun. Educational attainment is noticeably low, 57.812% had no formal education, and just 34.375% completed secondary education. Of the inmates, most respondents (43.75%) engaged in labor before imprisonment.

Family structure showed that 71.875% lived in joint family structures. Given the economic state, 70.312% owned their homes, while 37.5% reported earnings above 60,000 PKR. Notably, all respondents shared the barrack with more than 10 individuals, and 50% felt that overcrowding did not affect their health. Drug use was prevalent, with 93.75% using substances before incarceration, predominantly methamphetamine (68.75%). Awareness of HIV status was high, with 56.25% knowing their status prior to imprisonment, and 98.437% receiving treatment while incarcerated. However, 87.5% believed that HIV inmates did not receive a proper diet, indicating significant concerns about nutritional support. Despite the support and information available, 93.75% experienced stigmatization due to their HIV status. Hygiene practices among inmates were conditional: 100% of respondents stated they wash their hands with soap when available, but if they lack soap, they resort to washing with water only.

Conclusion

The prevalence of HIV is alarmingly rising among people who inject drugs (PWIDs). Evidence from the Integrated Behavioral and Biological Surveillance (IBBS) indicates that 38.5% of PWIDs were arrested in the past 12 months. This situation heightens the vulnerability of other prisoners, as PWIDs often have access to drugs within the prison system (National AIDS Control Program, 2016). Prisons represent one of the most restricted and marginalized settings for accessing health services, interventions, and surveys. Inmates are particularly vulnerable to acquiring infectious diseases like HIV, as individuals from diverse backgrounds, communities, and risk factors are confined together for extended periods (Khan et al., 2019). HIV and AIDS represent significant public health challenges for prisoners worldwide. These conditions pose serious issues for governments, public health systems, and prison administrations, emerging

as a major global concern having claimed an estimated 42.3 million lives to date, HIV/AIDS continues to spread across all countries worldwide. They have rapidly impacted millions of individuals across all ages and genders around the world (WHO, 2024). While there is no cure for HIV infection, it can be managed effectively with access to comprehensive prevention, diagnosis, treatment, and care—including for opportunistic infections. With these resources, HIV has become a manageable chronic condition, allowing individuals living with HIV to lead long and healthy lives (WHO, 2024).

The study sheds light on the complex interplay of various social factors affecting HIV-positive inmates in District Prison Malir, Karachi. Key findings reveal the significant impact of overcrowding, substance abuse, and social stigma on the well-being of these inmates. Roughly half of the participants stated that their health is unaffected by congestion, but approximately 27% said that it constantly has an effect on their health. This discrepancy emphasizes the critical need for initiatives to enhance living conditions in prisons and raises serious concerns about health outcomes associated with overcrowding. Financial hardship is pervasive; a significant percentage of households were renters (27%). Drug use was major issues (94%) of respondents reported using drugs prior to imprisonment, primarily methamphetamine (about 69%), since a large portion commit crimes under the influence of drugs.

Recommendations

1. The study observed that all HIV-positive inmates were housed together in a single barrack, which poses a high-risk factor. According to the inmates, the barrack is designed to accommodate 70-80 individuals, but the prison authorities overcrowd it with up to 150 inmates. It is suggested that the government establish additional jails to alleviate overcrowding and protect at-risk inmates from the associated dangers.

2. The study noted that most of the respondents were repeat offenders, indicating a high recidivism rate. To address this, it is recommended that habitual offenders be separated from new inmates to prevent the former from influencing the latter negatively. The government should consider establishing a separate facility or barrack specifically for recidivists.

Additionally, it was observed that recidivists were not ashamed of their crimes and were confident that they would receive bail. Therefore, it is suggested that the government implement stricter provisions to make it more difficult for recidivists to obtain bail easily.

3. The study observed that hygiene practices among HIV-positive inmates are nearly non-existent, particularly regarding handwashing after using the washroom due to the lack of soap. Since HIV-positive individuals already have weakened immune systems, the presence of germs on their hands poses a significant health risk, as hands and mouth are major routes of disease transmission. Therefore, it is recommended that jail authorities prioritize the hygiene practices of vulnerable inmates. Authorities should ensure that soap is provided to these inmates on a weekly basis. Additionally, the jail management could collaborate with soap manufacturing companies for sponsorship, enabling them to receive soap free of cost. This would not only improve the health and hygiene of vulnerable inmates but also help the department save money that could be utilized for other necessary expenditures such as building of new jails to address overcrowding issues, which is another critical challenge faced by the prison system.

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